

METHODS OF TEACHING PRONUNCIATION IN ENGLISH IN PRIMARY STAGE

Otaboyev Ahmadullo

Teacher of Andizhan state institute of foreign languages
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Annotation. The given article devoted to the specific features of teaching pronunciation to young learners at secondary schools. Using different approaches can improve the ways of teaching pronunciation. Mastery of sound structure is a prerequisite for communication in any form.

Key words: pronunciation, fluency, schoolchildren, skills and habits, foreign speech, aim.

English teachers in primary grades need to think through educational activities so that children develop pronunciation skills. Consequently, at present, the problem of developing pronunciation skills is relevant.

Often children do not have or have not fully developed pronunciation skills, so they cannot accurately pronounce a phrase in English.

Phonetics as an aspect of learning refers to the sound structure of a language - the totality of all sound means that make up its material side (sounds, sound combinations, stress, rhythm, melody, intonation, pauses).

Mastery of sound structure is a prerequisite for communication in any form. Speech will be understood with difficulty by the listener or not understood at all if he himself does not have pronunciation skills, since auditory images, or standards, accumulate in a person's auditory memory, and then what he hears is compared with what he has accumulated in your memory. During reading and writing, internal playback works, which means internal voicing and pronunciation. Consequently, only the presence of solid pronunciation skills ensures the normal functioning of all types of speech activity.[3]

There are two main approaches to teaching this aspect of language: acoustic and articulatory.

The acoustic approach consists of reproducing sounds by ear and imitating them. The assimilation of sounds occurs in the speech stream, and not in isolation. It is necessary to take into account the individual abilities of students to perceive and imitate rhythms and sounds, and it is also necessary to provide high-quality sound material. Obviously, that this practice does not guarantee a good result, since not everyone has good phonetic hearing.[4]

The articulatory approach includes a number of principles. First happens production of sounds (introductory phonetic course). To correctly produce sounds, each of which is practiced separately, students study the functioning of organs articulation when pronouncing each sound. Within this approach there are the following groups of phonemes: coinciding in both languages, non-coinciding and partially matching. The last two groups are the most difficult. The indisputable distinctive feature of this method is the creation of a system of phonetic exercises that allow you to master this aspect of the language quite well. Despite the

fact that the introductory phonetics course takes a lot of time. You can't talk about the purity of the skill. [1]

This approach involves the following stages of working with sound:

Orientation. The position of the organs of articulation when pronouncing sounds.

Planning. Putting the organs of articulation in the correct position.

Fixation. Preservation of the organs of articulation in the desired position is certain time to remember.

Sound processing. Reinforcing sound using phonetic exercises.

Pronunciation refers not only to the correct pronunciation of English sounds, but also to the intonation and expressiveness of speech.

Pronunciation skill is the ability to freely, quickly distinguish and recognize by ear the phonetic phenomena of a foreign language in someone else's speech, as well as to correctly and automatically pronounce the sounds of a foreign language separately and in the flow of speech, to intonate correctly. [3]

The goal of teaching pronunciation is to master the auditory-pronunciation side of speaking and reading:

- listening and hearing skills, development of phonemic hearing;

- pronunciation skills, i.e. mastery of the articulatory base of a foreign language and methods of intonation brought to automatism;

- development of internal speech (internal pronunciation) as the psychophysiological basis of external speech.

According to Filatova, the process of teaching pronunciation in primary and secondary schools is organized in accordance with the following principles.

Principles are a system of initial basic requirements for education and training, determining the content, forms and methods of the pedagogical process and ensuring its success. They reflect the internal essential aspects of the activities of the teacher and student, determine the effectiveness of training in various forms and its content. The principles express the normative foundations of learning. When teaching pronunciation, the following principles are used in the pedagogical process:

The principle of communicative orientation. Pronunciation training should be based on the need for communication. Primary perception occurs in the stream of speech, followed by processing of isolated sound. [5]

The principle of consciousness. This principle is achieved by explaining pronunciation, comparing sounds within a language, native and foreign, as well as using transcription, rules, instructions and visualization.

The principle of activity.

The principle of visibility (visual and auditory). This principle is implemented according to the rules: direct study of activity, based on observation, measurements and various types of activities. It is necessary to rationally combine words and visual images, use them wisely and in moderation. Visualization must correspond to the age characteristics of children.

Approximation principle.

The principle of taking into account the native language.

The principle of cultural conformity presupposes the maximum use of upbringing and education of the environment in which a particular educational institution is located. The

principle forms students' creative abilities and attitudes towards consumption, preservation, and creation of new cultural values.

The principle of accessibility and increasing difficulty. Educational material should gradually move from easy to complex, from unknown to known, taking into account the capabilities of each student.

The principle of connection between theory and practice. It expresses the need to prepare students for the correct use of theoretical knowledge in practice.

According to V.M. Filatov, the main requirements for pronunciation are phonemicity, i.e. the degree of correctness of the phonetic design of speech, sufficient for its understanding by the interlocutor, and fluency, i.e. degree of automation of pronunciation skills, allowing students to speak at a normal pace (130-150 words per minute).

Mastering correct pronunciation is possible only by mastering the phonetic base of a foreign language at the level of syllable, word stress, and intonation. In other words, students must learn the specifics of the articulatory base of a foreign language, as well as the characteristic features of stress and intonation.[6]

A skill is understood as a skill that has been brought to automaticity.

At the initial stage of training, two types of exercises are used:

Exercises for active listening and recognition of sounds and intonemes, aimed at developing phonetic hearing and establishing differential characteristics of the studied phonemes and intonemes. Exercises can be performed by ear and using a graphic support, with the teacher's voice or with a tape recorder. For example:

- listen to a series of sounds/words, raise your hand/signal card or clap your hands when you hear the sound [g]

- listen to the sentences, raise your hand when you hear an interrogative (declarative) sentence;

- listen to the sentence and mark stressed words/number of syntagmas, etc.

Reproduction exercises. They are aimed at active pronunciation (imitation) of sounds, syllables, phrases, sentences following a model teacher or speaker - in choir and individually.

So, at the initial stage of learning, it is necessary to lay the foundation for good pronunciation, which involves correct intonation, observing pauses, knowledge of the stress patterns of words in a sentence, as well as correct articulation. One of the means of improving pronunciation skills is phonetic exercise, the purpose of which is to anticipate and remove the appearance of possible phonetic difficulties (auditory-pronunciation, rhythmic-intonation), neutralize the influence of the sound environment in the native language, rebuild the articulatory apparatus from the Russian way of life to a foreign one, create and organize images of words by which students self-correct as standards.[2]

Pronunciation skill is the ability to freely and quickly distinguish and recognize by ear the phonetic phenomena of a foreign language in someone else's speech and correctly and automatically pronounce the sounds of a foreign language separately in the flow of speech, and correctly intonate.

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